

1 **Physicochemical, nutritional, microbiological, and cytotoxic**
2 **properties of freshly-squeezed raspberry fruit juice treated by**
3 **cold atmospheric pressure plasma, operated in a flowing mode**

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36 **Highlights:**

- 37 - Raspberry juice (RJ) was treated by cold atmospheric pressure plasma (CAPP)
- 38 - Physicochemical properties of RJ did not change after CAPP treatment
- 39 - Nutritional properties of RJ did not diverge post CAPP exposure
- 40 - After CAPP treatment, the number of viable microorganisms decreased
- 41 - Cytotoxic properties of RJ post exposure to CAPP were improved

42

43 **Abstract:** Consumption of different types of healthy nutritional products increased in the past
44 few years, due to a common trend of following healthy lifestyle by the society. Here, we have
45 studied an effect of cold atmospheric pressure plasma (CAPP) treatment on the
46 physicochemical, nutritional, microbiological, and cytotoxic properties of a freshly squeezed
47 raspberry juice (RJ) as we believe that CAPP-mediated preservation may be a tempting
48 alternative for the juice-processing sector. The so-produced RJ retains physicochemical and
49 nutritional properties, however, its microbiological and cytotoxic properties changed. CAPP-
50 treated RJ showed cytotoxicity towards human colon adenocarcinoma (Caco-2) cell lines.
51 Additionally, CAPP-exposure of artificially-inoculated RJ with *Escherichia coli* or
52 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* cells led to reductions of 100% and 73.2-79.5%, respectively, in
53 the numbers of colony forming units in the CAPP-treated juice. The herein-proposed
54 processing method might be helpful for achievement of longer storage periods for freshly
55 squeezed juice.

57

58 **Keywords:** freshly-squeezed fruit juice; non-thermal plasma; organic compounds profile;

59 proliferation activity; microorganisms; plasma-liquid interactions

60 **1. Introduction**

61 Improvement of the quality of fruit juices and other beverages caused by processes mediated
62 with the use of cold atmospheric pressure plasmas (CAPPs) are acknowledged to open quite a
63 new route in the non-thermal processing intended for food industry (Romulo & Kasih, 2023).
64 Physicochemical and biological effects of the short-lasting treatments of fruit juices by
65 different CAPP systems lead to changes in their chemical and microbial compositions,
66 occurring either immediately or post certain time period as has been compiled in a couple of
67 recent reviews (Fernandes & Rodrigues, 2008; Pohl *et al.*, 2022; Pravallika & Chakraborty,
68 2022; Putnik *et al.*, 2019; Romulo & Kasih, 2023; Ozen & Singh, 2020). As surveyed in these
69 papers, the short-lasting processing of fruit juices by a given CAPP source is expected to
70 inactivate various aerobic microorganisms (bacteria, yeasts and molds) that are responsible
71 for food spoilage, as well as to trigger degradation of endogenous enzymes responsible for
72 deterioration of the chemical quality and stability of the nourishment. Certainly, due to a
73 much shorter operation time and less intense thermal effects induced by CAPP during
74 treatment of fruit juices, this new non-thermal processing of fruit juices (and other food
75 products) seems very attractive for the manufacturers. From the consumers' point of view, the
76 nutritional values of juices treated in this way are maintained and even enhanced as was
77 described in the cited reviews (Fernandes & Rodrigues, 2008; Pohl *et al.*, 2022; Pravallika &
78 Chakraborty, 2022; Putnik *et al.*, 2019; Romulo & Kasih, 2023; Ozen & Singh, 2020). As
79 such, the CAPP processing seems to be a tempting alternative to commonly implemented
80 thermal sterilization and pasteurization processes.

81 Being a rich source of short- and long-lived reactive oxygen and nitrogen species
82 (RONS) and other radicals, depending on the discharge/plasma atmosphere, in addition to UV
83 photons and electrons of different energies, CAPP is capable of interacting with various
84 chemical components of fruit juices. These interactions, however, are rather non-invasive and
85 practically do not cause any unfavorable changes in the chemical structure and composition of
86 fruit juices that are typically responsible for instability or deterioration of the quality. On the
87 other hand, RONS show great antimicrobial properties towards bacterial and fungal
88 microorganisms, and therefore, their action leads to decontamination and sterilization of fruit
89 juices, and in consequence, the extension of their shelf life.

90 In addition to the review papers cited above, the number of original scientific papers
91 published in the last years clearly demonstrates the importance of this scientific problem *via*
92 attention paid to this issue. In reference to these works, it appears that different CAPP systems
93 have been used to control the activity of endogenous enzymes present in fruit juices, *i.e.*,

94 pectinmethylesterase (PME) (Andreou *et al.*, 2023), polyphenol oxidase (PPO) (Farias,
95 Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022), and peroxidase (POD) (Kumar, Pipliya & Srivastav, 2023;
96 Farias, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022), which are responsible for decreases in quality and
97 stability due to: the breakdown of pectin and the loss of cloud (PME), the browning (PPO),
98 and the discoloration in addition to the formation of off-flavors (PO).

99 The effects of the CAPP treatment on fruit juices is also researched considering,
100 firstly, the microbial inactivation and extension of the product shelf-life (Liu *et al.*, 2021), and
101 secondly, the maintenance of nutritive and sensorial quality of the juices (Liu *et al.*, 2021). In
102 the first case, the total viable count of all microorganisms, which covers typically aerobic
103 bacteria in addition to yeasts and molds (Park, Puligundla & Mok, 2021), is assessed before
104 and after CAPP treatment to determine whether the sterilization effect was achieved
105 (Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2022; Liu *et al.*, 2021; Park, Puligundla & Mok, 2021), or a certain
106 reduction in the number of viable microorganisms occurred, also in terms of the artificially
107 introduced model microorganisms like *Escherichia coli* (Hosseini *et al.*, 2021; Souza *et al.*,
108 2023), *Enterococcus faecalis* (Sohbatzadeh *et al.*, 2021), *Candida albicans* (Souza *et al.*,
109 2023), *Alicyclobacillus contaminans* (Wang *et al.*, 2023), *Alicyclobacillus acidoterrestris*
110 (Ding *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2022) or *Zygosaccharomyces rouxii* (Bao *et al.*, 2021). In the
111 second case, different chemical and physicochemical parameters have been assessed to check
112 eventual changes in the contents of CAPP-treated fruit juices regarding some selected
113 chemical compounds *e.g.* chlorophyll (Liu *et al.*, 2021), vitamin C (Liu *et al.*, 2021; Leite *et*
114 *al.*, 2021; Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2022; Souza *et al.*, 2023; Sohbatzadeh *et al.*, 2021), total
115 phenolics (Liu *et al.*, 2021; Leite *et al.*, 2021; Kumar *et al.*, 2023; Hosseini *et al.*, 2021;
116 Farias, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022; Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2022; Rodrigues, Rodrigues &
117 Fernandes, 2022; Souza *et al.*, 2023; Park, Puligundla & Mok, 2021), total flavonoids (Kumar,
118 Pipliya & Srivastav, 2023; Souza *et al.*, 2023), total anthocyanins (Park, Puligundla & Mok,
119 2021), total soluble solids (Kumera, Pipliya & Srivastac, 2023; Ding *et al.*, 2023; Souza *et al.*,
120 2023; Sohbatzadeh *et al.*, 2021; Park, Puligundla & Mok, 2021), the selected sugars or their
121 total sum (Leite *et al.*, 2021; Farias *et al.*, 2021; Ding *et al.*, 2023; Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2022;
122 Souza *et al.*, 2023; Sohbatzadeh *et al.*, 2021), certain amino acids (Leite *et al.*, 2021),
123 carboxylic acids (Leite *et al.*, 2021; Farias *et al.*, 2021; Sohbatzadeh *et al.*, 2021), volatile
124 compounds (alcohols, aldehydes, terpenoids) (Filho *et al.*, 2021; Rodrigues & Fernandes,
125 2022), or the chosen elements (Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2022). In addition, the antioxidant activity
126 (Kumera, Pipliya & Srivastac, 2023; Farias, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022; Rodriguez,
127 Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022; Souza *et al.*, 2023; Park, Puligundla & Mok, 2021), color (Liu

128 et al., 2021; Kumar, Pipliya & Srivastac, 2023; Hosseini *et al.*, 2021; Ding *et al.*, 2023;
129 Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2022; Souza *et al.*, 2023; Sohbatzadeh *et al.*, 2021), turbidity (Liu *et al.*,
130 2023), pH (Liu *et al.*, 2021; Kumar, Pipliya & Srivastac, 2023; Hosseini *et al.*, 2021; Ding *et*
131 *al.*, 2023; Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2022; Sohbatzadeh *et al.*, 2021; Park, Puligundla & Mok,
132 2021), or acidity (Liu *et al.*, 2023; Kumar, Pipliya & Srivastac, 2023; Ding *et al.*, 2023; Souza
133 *et al.*, 2023) have been so far measured.

134 All these studies concern juices prepared from common and popular fruits: apple
135 (Farias, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022; Farias *et al.*, 2021; Ding *et al.*, 2023; Bao *et al.*, 2021;
136 Wang *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2022), orange (Andreou *et al.*, 2023; Dzimitrowicz *et al.*,
137 2022; Souza *et al.*, 2023; Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022), kiwi (Liu *et al.*, 2023; Kumar,
138 Pipliya & Srivastac, 2023), pineapple (Sohbatzadeh *et al.*, 2021), sour cherry (Hosseini *et al.*,
139 2021), and chokeberry (Park, Puligundla & Mok, 2021), as well as quite exotic ones: cashew
140 apple (Miguel *et al.*, 2023; Leite *et al.*, 2021), acai (Rodriguez, Rodrigues & Fernandes,
141 2022), araca-boi (Farias *et al.*, 2023), caja (Rodriguez, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022), camu-
142 camu (Filho *et al.*, 2021), guava (Rodriguez, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022), and sapota
143 (Rodriguez, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022).

144 Considering the design of the before implemented CAPP systems, the overwhelming
145 majority of them, which is coincident with the herein cited reviews (Romulo & Kasih, 2023;
146 Pohl *et al.*, 2022; Pravallika & Chakraborty, 2022; Fernandes & Rodrigues, 2008; Ozen &
147 Singh, 2020; Putnik *et al.*, 2019), enable to treat fruit juices in a non-flow-through mode. As
148 such, small volumes of fruit juices, *i.e.*, 5 mL (Hosseini *et al.*, 2021; Souza *et al.*, 2023), 10
149 mL (Andreou *et al.*, 2023; Hosseini *et al.*, 2021; Rodriguez, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022),
150 15 mL (Hosseini *et al.*, 2021; Leite *et al.*, 2021; Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022), 18 mL (Liu *et*
151 *al.*, 2023), 20 mL (Miguel *et al.*, 2023; Leite *et al.*, 2021; Farias, Rodrigues & Fernandes,
152 2022; Farias *et al.*, 2021), 30 mL (Farias *et al.*, 2023) or 40 mL (Filho *et al.*, 2021) can be
153 processed at once. Extremely rarely, a greater volume, *e.g.*, 330 mL (Ding *et al.*, 2023) has
154 been treated by CAPP. As the formerly utilized CAPP sources, the following discharges
155 dominate: dielectric barrier discharges (DBDs) sustained in a form of gaseous (He, Ar, Ar
156 admixed with O₂, or air) plasma jets (PJs) (Andreou *et al.*, 2023; Hosseini *et al.*, 2021;
157 Sohbatzadeh *et al.*, 2021; Park, Puligundla & Mok, 2021) or operated in planar chambers in
158 surrounding air (P-DBDs) (Filho *et al.*, 2021; Liu *et al.*, 2023; Miguel *et al.*, 2023; Leite *et*
159 *al.*, 2021; Kumar, Pipliya & Srivastac, 2023; Farias *et al.*, 2023; Farias, Rodrigues &
160 Fernandes, 2022; Farias *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2023; Souza *et al.*, 2023; Sohbatzadeh *et*
161 *al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2022). DBD can also be sustained in cylindrical chambers (C-DBDs)

162 (Ding *et al.*, 2023; Bao *et al.*, 2021), in which fruit juices, percolated with air, form the
163 ground electrode of the discharge system. To faithfully reflect the state of scientific research,
164 low pressure glow discharge (LPGD) sources, sustained in N₂ or synthetic air, should also be
165 mentioned (Filho *et al.*, 2021; Farias *et al.*, 2023; Farias, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022;
166 Farias *et al.*, 2021; Rodriguez, Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022), however, their operation is
167 more demanding due to requirement for a vacuum. Among all these CAPP systems, the one
168 exception is atmospheric pressure glow discharge system (APGD) (Dzimitrowicz *et al.*,
169 2022), sustained in surrounding air and in contact with the continuously flowing juice,
170 forming the cathode of the system. In this case, the volume of the treated juice is unlimited,
171 since the system is working as a flow-through and enables collection of the CAPP-treated
172 juice during operation of the discharge.

173 Poland is the leader among the EU countries and the world's number-five raspberry
174 producer. The production and consumption of these brambles have increased in the recent
175 years and the reason for that is the very high content of anthocyanins, which are bioactive
176 compounds known to reduce the blood glucose level and stabilize the blood lipid profile
177 (Pina-Contreras *et al.*, 2022; Tao *et al.*, 2023). Considering the fruit structure of raspberries
178 and their higher respiration rate as compared to other aggregate fruits, these brambles easily
179 spoil because of various types of microorganisms, regardless of whether they are fresh or
180 frozen (Velebit *et al.*, 2022; Bovi *et al.*, 2019). Hence, the perishability of raspberry juices
181 (RJs), prepared from fresh or frozen fruits, tends to be high as well. Reflecting this, it should
182 not be surprising that the development of minimal processing methods to sterilize fresh RJs
183 without a special thermal input, and hence, enabling to maintain health-promoting and
184 nutritional properties of these juices, would be of special significance for the food industry
185 and technology. Additionally, natural products have gained attention for their potential to
186 prevent and treat diseases due to their low toxicity, minimal side effects, and ability to target
187 multiple aspects of diseases at once (Crooker *et al.* 2018). Various studies have highlighted
188 the effectiveness of natural compounds such as phenols, flavonoids, alkaloids, and terpenoids
189 showing anti-cancer activity (Wang & Jiang, 2012). Natural products like epimedium,
190 resveratrol, and silymarin have shown promising antioxidant, anti-angiogenic, and anti-
191 metastatic properties in both preclinical and clinical studies (Moghadam *et al.*, 2022; Balahbib
192 *et al.*, 2021). Fruits are rich sources of bioactive compounds and are widely recognized as
193 functional foods due to their pleasant taste and health benefits. It is well established that
194 bioactive molecules of berries exhibit regulatory effects on carcinogen and xenobiotic
195 metabolizing enzymes, as well as on various transcription and growth factors, inflammatory

196 cytokines, and subcellular signaling pathways involved in cancer cell proliferation, apoptosis,
197 and tumor angiogenesis (Rahmani, Babiker & Anwar, 2023; Kim *et al.*, 2022). Moreover,
198 these phytochemicals have the potential to sensitize tumor cells to chemotherapeutic agents
199 by inhibiting pathways associated with resistance to the applied treatment. In addition,
200 consumption of berry fruits may offer some level of protection lowering toxicity associated
201 with cancer therapy (Seeram, 2008).

202 Since the vast majority of research works reported the use of non-flow-through CAPP
203 systems, a continuous-flow CAPP system, based on APGD in contact with a flowing liquid
204 cathode (FLC), was proposed in the present contribution to treat the first home-made RJ
205 without changing its nutritional properties. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study
206 in which comprehensive analyses of the compounds profile, elemental composition, in
207 addition to cytotoxic properties of the freshly-squeezed RJ were estimated post CAPP
208 treatment. In more detail, FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ was examined at first in reference to its
209 chemical composition, including the profile of volatile compounds as determined by gas
210 chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS), the non-volatile compounds profile assessed
211 by high-performance liquid chromatography with the UV-Vis diode-array detection (HPLC-
212 DAD), the total elements contentment as measured by inductively coupled plasma optical
213 emission spectrometry (ICP OES), preceded by the wet digestion of the relevant samples of
214 RJ. These analyses were complemented by revealing the pH and color. Furthermore, the
215 proliferation activity of the studied CAPP-exposed RJ was estimated towards human colon
216 carcinoma cells (Caco-2) and normal human intestinal epithelial cell line *i.e.*, FHs 74 Int.
217 Next, artificial inoculations of RJ with model microorganisms *Escherichia coli* or
218 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* followed by CAPP treatment were applied to assess the ability of
219 FLC-dc-APGD system to effectively inactivate microbial cells from RJ, in relation to avoiding
220 food spoilage. Finally, the CAPP-liquid interactions responsible for the defined
221 physicochemical, nutritional, and biological properties of RJ, have been determined.

222

223 **2. Materials and Methods**

224 *2.1. Raspberry juice preparation*

225 The RJ has been freshly squeezed according to the following protocol from raspberries
226 cv. Lagorai acquired from a local market. Fresh raspberries (1000 g) were placed in a 2-L
227 beaker, sterilized before with 70% ethyl alcohol, and blended using a hand blender up to the
228 point of reaching a uniform consistency of the homogenate. Then, this pulp was initially
229 filtered through sterile cotton gauze, while the resulting filtrate (600 mL) was equally divided

230 and centrifuged at 10,000 rounds/min for 10 mins. The collected supernatants were combined
231 and used in the further experiments. One part of the so-prepared RJ was directly treated by a
232 flow-through FLC-dc-APGD system to assess later on eventual changes in the chemical
233 composition of the CAPP-treated RJ. The other part of RJ was sterilized in microjet
234 microwave sterilizer (Enbio) autoclave at 120°C. Post cooling down, the so-sterilized freshly
235 squeezed RJ has been used for microbiological analyses including artificial inoculation with
236 model microorganisms (either with *E. coli* or *S. cerevisiae*; Table 1).

237

238 *2.2. Cold atmospheric pressure plasma source*

239 RJ was treated using a CAPP-based flow-through system (polish patent application no.
240 P.447139 from 18/12/2023). In this CAPP-based system RJ was introduced to the quartz
241 chamber, being a zone of discharge, by a peristaltic pump (Core Palmer, Masterflex L/S). The
242 flow rate of RJ was set to be 4.5 mL min⁻¹. Pumping of the RJ to the quartz chamber was
243 carried out using a silicone hose (no. 13, Core Palmer, Masterflex L/S) connected to the
244 quartz tube (OD= 4.0 mm). A 3 mm above the quartz tube, a graphite tube (OD= 9.8 mm) was
245 placed. Additionally, in the 5 mm gap between the edge of the graphite tube and the
246 exacerbated tungsten electrode, CAPP in the form of FLC-dc-APGD was ignited by supplying
247 to the system an 1100 V voltage (dc HV) power supply from dc generator (DSC-Electronics,
248 Germany, model DP50H-024PH). The current value of 50 mA was maintained. The portions
249 of the freshly-squeezed RJ or freshly-squeezed RJ initially sterilized and subsequently
250 inoculated with bacteria RJ were subjected to the FLC-dc-APGD ignited in the flow-through
251 CAPP-based system. After subjecting the RJ to FLC-dc-APGD, it was collected to sterile
252 vials for further studies.

253

254 *2.3. Assessment of physicochemical and nutritional properties of RJ*

255 *2.3.1. The volatile compounds profile of RJ determined by GC-MS*

256 Gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was applied for qualitative
257 determination of volatile compounds in the untreated and FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ. At first,
258 volatile compounds were extracted using solid phase microextraction (SPME) in a head space
259 (HS) mode. The 3-mL samples of RJ were introduced to 10-mL HS glass vials with 1 g of
260 NaCl and subjected to pre-equilibration for 30 min. Then, an adsorption fiber was introduced
261 to the HS vial through a silicone-Teflon septum. The sorption of the volatile compounds was
262 performed for 30 min. Afterwards, the fiber was taken back to a holder, while a needle of the
263 holder was introduced to another vial filled with N₂ (with precautions of the adsorption of

264 some volatile compounds from ambient air), and transported for the analysis by GC-MS. The
265 GC-MS analysis was performed using a Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010 SE system with an
266 Agilent polar column DB-624 (length 20 m, ID 0.18 mm, film thickness 1 μm). The following
267 temperature program was used: starting temperature 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ hold by 1 min, then 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to
268 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, then 16 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 230 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 5 min hold in 230 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The splitless injection was used. The
269 pressure of He was 100 kPa. The MS detector was operated to scan the masses between 35 to
270 600 m/z. The EI source was operated in 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The qualitative analysis was performed using
271 the NIST mass spectra library.

272

273 2.3.2. *The non-volatile compounds profile of RJ estimated by HPLC-DAD*

274 High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with diode array detector (DAD) was used
275 to determine the profiles of non-volatile organic compounds in the untreated and CAPP-
276 treated RJ. A prominence modular HPLC system from Shimadzu with a Gemini NX-C18
277 column (5 μm , C18 110A, 150 mm \times 4.6 mm, Phenomenex) were used for chromatographic
278 separations. The mobile phase was A: ammonium formate buffer (10 mM, pH 3.1) with B:
279 HPLC-grade acetonitrile (POCH, Poland). The injection volume was 25 μL . A flow rate of
280 the mobile phase was 1 mL min^{-1} . The column oven was set to 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The elution gradient
281 started from 5% of B, and increased to 65% of B in 13 mins. The DAD was set to measure the
282 spectra of the outcoming eluate in the range from 200 to 700 nm.

283

284 2.3.3. *pH and color of RJ*

285 An Elmetron (Poland) pH meter (CPC-505) was used to measure pH of the untreated and the
286 FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ. The pH meter was calibrated using three Mettler-Toledo pH
287 buffers with pH 4.01, 7.00, and 9.21.

288 Eplaneta (Poland) colorimeter, model 4-Wave WR-18, was applied to measure color
289 indexes in the CIE *Lab* color space, *i.e.*, *L* for lightness (values from 0 to 100), *a* for
290 increments from red to green (values \pm 150), and *b* for increments from yellow to blue (values
291 \pm 150). In addition, the difference between two colors in the CIE *Lab* color space was
292 calculated as $\Delta E = \sqrt{(\Delta L)^2 + (\Delta a)^2 + (\Delta b)^2}$, and as the chroma (*C*), $C = \sqrt{(\Delta a)^2 + (\Delta b)^2}$.

293

294 2.3.4. *Concentration of the elements assessed by ICP-OES*

295 Prior to the quantitative determination of the selected elements (Al, Ba, Ca, Cu, Fe, K, Mg,
296 Mn, Na, Sr, Zn) in untreated *versus* CAPP-treated freshly squeezed RJ, the investigated

297 samples underwent wet digestion. For this purpose, a SCP Science digestion block, model
298 DigiPREP Jr. was used. Samples of RJ (1.0 g) were weighted into special 50-mL
299 DigiTUBES, 2.0 mL of the concentrated HNO₃ was added, the tubes were covered, and
300 placed within the digestion block set to 120 °C. The digestion of samples under this
301 temperature lasted for 2 hours, until the volume of solutions in DigiTUBES decreased to less
302 than 0.5 mL. Afterwards, 1.0 mL of 30% H₂O₂ solution was added, the digestion process was
303 prolonged for the next 1 h, until the reagent completely decayed and the volume of the
304 solutions was again less than 0.5 mL. These remnants were reconstituted with water to 20.0 g.
305 So-digested samples were filtered through 0.45 mm Nylon® syringe filters. The concentrations
306 of Al, Ba, Cu, Fe, Mn, Na, Sr, and Zn were directly measured in the samples solutions
307 prepared in the above-described manner. In the case of measurements of the concentrations of
308 Ca, K and Mg, these samples were diluted 10 times (Ca, Mg) and 100 times (K) prior to
309 analysis. Agilent synchronous vertical dual view ICP OES instrument, model 5110, with a
310 Seaspray nebulizer and a cyclonic spray chamber for the pneumatic nebulization, was used to
311 conduct these measurements. The analysis was carried out considering standard working
312 parameters of the instrument, as recommend by its manufacturer. The method was calibrated
313 using 5 multielement standards solutions at the concentrations ranging from 0.05 to 5.00 µg g⁻¹
314 ¹.

315

316 2.4. Cytotoxic properties

317 The Caco-2 cell line (ATCC HTB-37), originating from human colonic adenocarcinoma, was
318 procured from the ATCC collection. The FHs 74 Int normal human intestinal epithelial cell
319 line (ATCC CCL-241) was immortalized using a previously documented method to establish
320 stable cell lines (Kraskiewicz *et al.*, 2020). Both cell lines were utilized to investigate the
321 effects of exposure to FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ or untreated RJ on cell viability. The cells
322 were cultured in Opti-MEM with GlutaMAX medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.),
323 supplemented with 2% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco), 100 U mL⁻¹ penicillin, and 100 µg
324 mL⁻¹ streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich), and maintained at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ atmosphere. Upon
325 reaching confluency, the cells were routinely subcultured using 0.05% trypsin/0.02% EDTA
326 (w/v) solution. To assess the impact of the FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ on Caco-2 and FHs 74
327 Int cell lines, the cells were exposed to the diluted samples of RJ that had undergone FLC-dc-
328 APGD treatment (FLC-dc-APGD RJ group) or remained untreated (UNTR RJ group).
329 Initially, *in vitro* experiments were conducted using ×1000, ×100, ×25, and ×10 dilutions of
330 FLC-dc-APGD-treated and untreated RJ in a serum-free culture medium. A control group was

331 included using a culture medium without serum for all experiments. The cytotoxic properties
332 were estimated using MTT assay conducted following the methodology outlined in our
333 previously published papers (Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2022; Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2020). The FLC-
334 dc-APGD-treated and untreated RJ samples were centrifuged (12 000 x g, 15 min) and the
335 supernatant was filtered before using in all the *in vitro* tests. Next, in brief, FHs 74 Int cells
336 were seeded at a concentration of 5×10^3 cells per well and Caco-2 cells at 5×10^3 cells per
337 well in dedicated 96-well plates. Opti-MEM with GlutaMAX medium supplemented with 100
338 U mL⁻¹ penicillin and 100 µg mL⁻¹ streptomycin was utilized to provide optimal growth
339 conditions for the cells, without the addition of fetal bovine serum. On the next day, the cells
340 were exposed for FLC-APGD-treated or untreated RJ solutions at different dilutions of
341 $\times 1000$, $\times 100$, $\times 25$, and $\times 10$. Dilutions were prepared in serum-free culture medium (Opti-
342 MEM), for each group in duplicate. After 24 and 72 hrs of incubation, 100 µL of 0.4 mg mL⁻¹
343 MTT solution was added to each well and incubated in the dark at 37 °C for 3 hrs.
344 Subsequently, the MTT solution was replaced with 100 µL of DMSO and incubated at 37 °C
345 for 10 mins to dissolve the purple crystals formed. The optical density (OD) value of the
346 resulting mixtures was measured at 570 nm using a Victor 2 multi-function microplate reader
347 (Perkin Elmer, USA). To determine metabolic activity, the mean OD readings obtained from
348 duplicates in 3 independent experiments were calculated. Before treatment the cells with MTT
349 solution at the same time points (24 hrs and 72 hrs) were visualized using an Axio Observer
350 inverted microscope equipped with a dry 10x objective (Zeiss, Gottingen, Germany). The
351 images were processed with the Zen Blue software (Zeiss, Gottingen, Germany).

352

353 2.5. Inactivation of microorganisms from the artificially inoculated RJ

354 Microbial suspensions for artificial inoculations were prepared as follows. The culture of the
355 tested microorganism (*Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 or *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* FM26;
356 Table 1) in liquid growth medium (TSB or Sabouraud, respectively; Table 1) has been
357 centrifuged (10000 rpm, 10 mins) and the cell pellet has been washed twice in sterile
358 physiological saline to get rid of the medium residuals. The optical density of the so-obtained
359 cell suspension has been adjusted to 0.5 in McFarland (McF) scale with the use of
360 physiological saline and densitometer DEN-1B (BioSan, Riga, Latvia). 50 µL of the 0.5 McF
361 suspension of microbial cells has been used for artificial inoculation of 6 mL of the freshly
362 squeezed RJ, which was before sterilized with the use of Microjet microwave sterilizer
363 (Enbio, Rumia, Poland) and cooled down. The artificially inoculated (either with *E. coli* or *S.*
364 *cerevisiae*) RJ has been subjected to the action of FLC-dc-APGD generated in the continuous

365 flow system, as described in *section 2.2*. As the controls, the artificially inoculated (either
366 with *E. coli* or *S. cerevisiae*) RJ samples have been passed through the plasma-generating
367 system, but without plasma ignition. Post CAPP action, the so-treated RJ, in addition to the
368 corresponding controls, have been serially diluted to 10^{-6} in sterile physiological saline and
369 100 μL of each of the prepared dilutions has been plated on the appropriate solid medium
370 (TSA or Sabouraud + agar; Table 1). Moreover, the samples of the sterilized RJ have been
371 plated on TSA plates to confirm effectiveness of the action of the Microjet microwave
372 sterilizer. Subsequently, the plates have been incubated at the optimal conditions for each of
373 the investigated microorganisms (Table 1). Then, the colonies grown on the solid media have
374 been counted and percentage reductions in addition to logarithmic reductions in the microbial
375 viable counts have been determined. The herein-described experiment has been conducted in
376 a triplicate.

377

378 *2.6. Plasma-liquid interactions*

379 Plasma-liquid interactions were revealed basing on several experimental techniques. At the
380 beginning, short-lived individuals generated during FLC-dc-APGD treatment of RJ were
381 determined by optical emission spectrometry (OES). Here, optical emission spectra from the
382 gaseous zone of the discharge were collected in order to identify the RONS produced in the
383 gaseous phase of the discharge. In more details, the FLC-dc-APGD operated in the contact
384 with a flowing RJ was captured using an UV achromatic lens ($f=60$), while the radiation was
385 collimated on the slit entrance (10 μm) of OES spectrometer (Shamrock SR-500i, Andor).
386 This OES spectrometer was coupled with a CCD camera (Newton DU-920P-0E, Andor). The
387 setup for measurements was operated in full vertical binning mode (FVB) with integration
388 time of 1-s. The OES measurements were acquired using holographic gratings 1800 lines nm^{-1}
389 for 200-400 nm ranges, while for 400-900 nm ranges with 1200 lines nm^{-1} gratings PG-5 cut-
390 off filter (<385 nm) was applied to exclude second-order radiation. Additionally, the OES
391 measurements, data collection, and processing were performed *via* Solis S software (Andor,
392 UK).

393 To reveal the contribution of reactive oxygen species into the occurring plasma-liquid
394 interactions, colorimetric methods were employed to estimate the concentrations of H_2O_2 and
395 NO_2^- .

396 The contents of H_2O_2 in the untreated and FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ were determined
397 using Amplex Red assay kit (Invitrogen, USA). Before running these analyses, the reagents
398 were incubated at the room temperature. Afterwards, the working solutions of the reagents

399 were prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions. A standard H₂O₂ solution was
400 used to prepare a 6-point calibration curve (0-10 μM). Immediately after FLC-dc-APGD
401 treatment of RJ, the samples of the untreated and CAPP-treated RJ were diluted 10, 20, and
402 40 times to fit within the calibration plot. 50 μL of standard solutions for calibration plot and
403 FLC-dc-APGD-treated and untreated RJ samples were transferred into the test black 96 well-
404 plate. Finally, the examined samples were supplemented with the defined working solutions
405 according to the manufacturer's instructions, and incubated at room temperature in the dark
406 for 30 min. The fluorescence measurements were performed using excitation at 530 nm, and
407 detection of emission was conducted at 590 nm. These measurements were performed using a
408 Jasco spectrofluorometer (model F8500) coupled with FMP-825 fluorescence microplate
409 reader.

410 Because monitoring the concentration of NO₂⁻ is crucial to assure the safety of the
411 juice (after ISO 6635 standard), we have performed studies in which the content of NO₂⁻ in
412 the untreated and FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ was revealed according to the requirements of
413 ISO 6635. At the beginning, 0.2% (m/v) solution of sulfanilamide (Solution 1), 0.1% (m/v)
414 solution of N-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride (Solution 2), and 16.5% (m/v)
415 solution of HCl (Solution 3) were prepared. Afterwards, the untreated and FLC-dc-APGD RJ
416 samples were centrifuged in a volume 10 mL for 10 min at 6,000 rpm, and the supernatant
417 was collected and filtered *via* a syringe filter 35 μm. Next, the samples were 2 or 10 times
418 diluted and transferred in the volume of 10 mL into 50 mL volumetric flasks. The flasks were
419 filled with deionized water to approximately 30 mL, and then 5 mL of Solution 1 and 3 mL of
420 Solution 3 were introduced. Subsequently, the solutions were mixed. In the final stage, 1 mL
421 of Solution 2 was added and the content of the volumetric flask was mixed and left for 3 min
422 at room temperature in the dark. Post this action, the resultant solution was filled with
423 deionized water up to the mark and mixed again. The absorbance values were measured at
424 538 nm in 15 min post preparation using a UV/Vis absorption spectrophotometer (Specord
425 210 Plus, Analytik Jena). For the 6-point calibration plot, sodium nitrite was used to prepare
426 500 mg L⁻¹ of NO₂⁻ standard solution. Finally, the calibration plot was plotted basing on
427 assessments of properly diluted 500 mg L⁻¹ standard solution within the range 0-3 mg L⁻¹ post
428 introduction into 50 mL volumetric flasks and examination in the same manner as for the RJ
429 samples.

430 The measurements of the concentrations of H₂O₂ and NO₂⁻ were performed in three
431 independent experiments and presented as mean values with a standard deviation.

432

433 2.7. *Statistical analyses*

434 The two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to investigate the statistical
435 significance of the observed differences. The comparisons between untreated and FLC-dc-
436 APGD-treated RJ solutions were conducted *via* Tukey's multiple comparisons *post-hoc* test.
437 For the MTT experiments, the graphical presentation of the collected results, along with the
438 conducted statistical analyses, was achieved using GraphPad Prism 8.0 software (GraphPad
439 Software, USA). The comparison of the investigated groups versus the control group was
440 made using the one-way ANOVA with the Dunnett's *post-hoc* test.

441

442 **3. Results and discussion**

443 3.1. *Volatile and non-volatile compounds profiles of RJ*

444 Figure 1 presents GC-MS chromatograms of the untreated and the CAPP-treated RJ. As can
445 be noted, there were no differences in the composition of volatile compounds identified for RJ
446 after its FLC-dc-APGD treatment. Chromatographic peaks representing volatile compounds
447 separated in the untreated and the FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ overlapped. Since SPME is
448 regarded as semi-quantitative, total ion current peaks should not be directly compared.
449 Nevertheless, excluding the peak at the retention time of 13.3 min, the height of the remaining
450 chromatographic peaks was comparable, pointing out that the FLC-dc-APGD treatment did
451 not change the profile of volatile compounds present in RJ. In addition, Table 2 depicts the
452 list of substances identified with a higher than 90% matching with the reference library of
453 spectra. Despite hexyl-hydroxyperoxide, all the found compounds are among the most often
454 detected in RJ juice (Aprea *et al.*, 2015). The hexyl-hydroxyperoxide can be a marker of
455 processing, such as grinding, which might have activated specific enzymes (Aprea *et al.*,
456 2009).

457 Different results were obtained in the case of orange juice treated by a PE-50 gas
458 discharge plasma system (Rodrigues & Fernandes, 2022). In the case of the above-mentioned
459 treatment, the profile of volatile compounds turn out to be significantly affected by the CAPP
460 exposure, likely also to a relatively long processing of this juice, *i.e.*, the treatment times were
461 changed from 10 to 30 min. A less relevant influence of DBD atmospheric plasma and glow
462 discharge plasma, operated under different atmosphere, on the profile of volatile compounds
463 has been measured in camu-camu juice (Filho *et al.*, 2021).

464 Later on non-volatile compounds profiles were deciphered for the untreated and FLC-
465 dc-APGD-treated RJ, as assessed using HPLC-DAD, while the spectra were acquired at the
466 universal 254 nm wavelength for compounds that possess absorption properties. It appeared

467 that the CAPP treatment of RJ practically did not change the chemical composition of the RJ
468 matrix (Figure 2). Both registered HPLC-DAD chromatograms easily overlapped, considering
469 the vast majority of chromatographic peaks. Furthermore, the height of these peaks was
470 practically the same, although, there were some exceptions, *e.g.*, the highly increased peak at
471 2.0 min (dispersive peak), likely due to an increased salt content, and the slightly increased
472 peak at 7.9 min.

473 Generally, as shown by GC-MS and HPLC-DAD analyses, the use of the flow-through
474 FLC-dc-APGD system did not change the profiles of volatile and non-volatile organic
475 compounds in this product. The construction of the applied system not only assured unlimited
476 amounts of the CAPP-treated RJ, but also a relatively short contact time of CAPP with the
477 components of RJ, causing rather minor deviations in the composition of the so-treated RJ.

478

479 3.2. pH and color

480 The applied FLC-dc-APGD-treatment in the developed CAPP system did not result in
481 changes in the pH of RJ. The pH of the untreated RJ equaled 2.74 ± 0.01 , while after its
482 processing with FLC-dc-APGD the determined pH value was 2.72 ± 0.03 . Therefore, ΔpH was
483 insignificant, which might be associated with a short contact time of RJ with the CAPP
484 components; the superficially treated RJ is in reality continuously replenished by its fresh,
485 untreated portion. High buffering capacity of RJ could also mask the eventual changes in pH
486 that are caused by the formation of some RONS, *i.e.*, HNO_3 and HNO_2 (Pohl *et al.*, 2022;
487 Fernandes & Rodrigues, 2021). Lack of the pH reduction in RJ by its FLC-dc-APGD-
488 treatment could also indicate that the eventual inactivation of microorganisms would not
489 occur due to the acidification of so-exposed RJ.

490 The results of measurements of *L*, *a*, and *b* color indexes are given in Table 3. There
491 was practically no difference in lightness of the untreated and CAPP-treated RJ. Changes in
492 two other color indexes, directly related with chroma, were also small, *i.e.*, -13.3% for *a*, and -
493 8.4% for *b*. Nevertheless, the chroma of FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ decreased from 4.58 ± 0.03
494 to 4.04 ± 0.04 (by 11.8%), and it was mostly linked with a decrease of red/green increments.
495 The overall difference in color was lower than 1.0, *i.e.*, $\Delta E=0.56\pm 0.02$, hence, a standard
496 observer could not see the difference related to the CAPP-treatment of RJ. This outcome was
497 coincident with the results of HPLC-DAD analysis, in which no significant differences were
498 found in the content of soluble in water organic compounds.

499

500 3.3. Concentrations of elements

501 Results on concentrations of elements in the untreated and the CAPP-treated RJ are given in
502 Table 4. As can be noted, except for Ca, Na, and Zn, there was no difference in the
503 concentration of elements determined in the untreated and the FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ. This
504 observation pointed out that no water evaporation occurred, as the contact time of the APGD
505 phase with the surface of the introduced RJ was relatively short. In addition, it was a direct
506 proof that the action of the herein applied FLC-dc-APGD system was indeed non-thermal.
507 Recently, in a similar CAPP system (Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2022), no significant differences in
508 the concentrations of the determined elements due to the non-thermal effect of APGD and the
509 negligible water evaporation were also recorded for a CAPP-exposed orange juice. In the case
510 of Ca, Na, and Zn, an increase in the concentration of these elements was established,
511 however, it could be related with contamination of RJ, likely occurring in the FLC
512 compartment during contact of the acidic RJ with materials building up the discharge
513 chamber.

514

515 3.4. Proliferation activity of cells exposed to RJ

516 The Caco-2 cell line, representing the human intestinal epithelium, has been recognized as a
517 suitable *in vitro* model for assessing the bioavailability of metal ions from various food
518 products and beverages according to the previous studies (Matusiewicz *et al.*, 2019;
519 Ramazzina *et al.*, 2016). Accordingly, the current study aimed to evaluate the proliferation
520 activity of Caco-2 cells, representing human colon adenocarcinoma, and FHs 74 Int cells, a
521 normal human intestinal epithelial cell line after subjection to RJ-treated with FLC-dc-APGD
522 or the non-treated control. This assessment was conducted using the MTT assay to elucidate
523 any potential anti-proliferative effects of FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ.

524 As is shown in Figure 3, not only 10 times diluted FLC-dc-APGD- treated RJ, but also
525 10 times diluted untreated RJ turned out to be cytotoxic for the Caco-2 cell line in a short-
526 term observation (24 hrs) compared to the control (UNTR RJ * $p < 0.05$, FLC-dc-APGD RJ
527 ** $p < 0.01$, vs. CONTROL). FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ did not show any significant growth
528 inhibition towards normal human intestinal epithelial cell line FHs 74 Int compared to the
529 control RJ within 24 hrs observation.

530 Longer observations (72 h) confirmed growth inhibition, significant for Caco-2 and
531 FHs 74 Int cells at 10x dilution. Moderate growth inhibition was observed for both cell lines
532 in terms of 10 times dilution of the untreated and FLC-dc-APGD treated RJ with statistically
533 significant differences (** $p < 0.01$ and *** $p < 0.001$ vs. CONTROL). It is clearly shown that

534 FLC-dc-APGD treatment did not adversely affect the nutritional properties of RJ for the
535 investigated cells at various dilutions ($\times 1000$, $\times 100$, and $\times 25$), preserving its bioactive
536 components from degradation. Only for Caco-2 cells statistically significant reductions in
537 metabolic activity were observed for FLC-dc-APGD-treated *versus* untreated RJ at 10 times
538 dilutions for 72 hrs (FLC-dc-APGD RJ versus UNTR RJ, $**p < 0.01$).

539 The obtained results align with the previous findings on the selective cytotoxic activity
540 of pure potato juice against cancer and normal colon cells. The cytotoxic activity of individual
541 bioactive compounds in PJ was concerned showing that glycoalkaloids exhibit concentration-
542 dependent cytotoxicity against all the analyzed cell lines (including cancerous and non-
543 cancerous cells) (Kowalczewski *et al.*, 2022). Moreover, some investigations proved that
544 pomegranate juice after subjection to *in vivo* metabolism affects the proliferation and
545 migration of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) cell lines besides inducing apoptosis in these
546 cells. This investigation showed that pomegranate juice exerts its inhibitory effects on HCC
547 cells by inducing mitochondrial dysfunction (Zhou *et al.*, 2024). In another study, the authors
548 proved that the UV-treated apple juice showed no cytotoxic effect on normal intestinal cells,
549 but inhibited at the same time the growth of human colon cancer cells (Islam *et al.*, 2016). In a
550 separate investigation, a water-soluble fraction of the soursop fruit pulp showed potential as a
551 cytotoxic agent against breast cancer (MCF-7) and human colon carcinoma cells (Caco-2),
552 primarily by disrupting cell membrane integrity, while showing less significant effects on
553 hepatic cells (HepG2).

554 In this study the effects of fruit pulp on mitochondrial metabolism and membrane
555 integrity by performance of the cytotoxicity assays have been explored. These investigations
556 revealed promising indications of fruit pulp's therapeutic potential against specific cancer
557 types (Scharf *et al.*, 2024). On the other hand, some results showed a significant increase in
558 cytotoxicity in Caco-2 cells treated with digesta, particularly those containing sausage and/or
559 white chocolate, compared to the control conditions. Interestingly, the levels of cytotoxicity
560 were not as high as in the cells exposed to orange juice, coffee, curcuma, or soda beverages
561 (Vahid *et al.*, 2024). The other anti-cancer mechanism was postulated in the study of Tatar *et*
562 *al.*, (2019). There, the telomerase activity in six human colorectal cancer cells decreased
563 significantly after treatment with blackberry extract, with even a small concentration
564 effectively blocking telomerase activity in cell lysates. Importantly, the inhibitory effect of
565 blackberry on telomerase activity was more pronounced in cancer cells compared to normal
566 PBMCs. Furthermore, blackberry treatment reduced the expression of human telomerase
567 reverse transcriptase (hTERT) and its promoter methylation in cancer cell lines, indicating

568 that telomerase inhibition may be a key mechanism underlying blackberry's anticancer effects
569 in cancer cells (Tatar *et al.*, 2019). A very interesting study from year 2007 showed that
570 colon-available raspberry extract exhibited reduced levels of anthocyanins and ellagitannins
571 compared to the original RJ, yet it was enriched in other polyphenols and their breakdown
572 products, which showed increased stability during gastrointestinal digestion. This extract
573 demonstrated significant protective effects against DNA damage induced by H₂O₂ in HT29
574 colon cancer cells and led to a notable decrease in the population of HT29 cells in the G1
575 phase of the cell cycle, effectively hindering the progression of cells into the cell cycle.
576 Moreover, the raspberry extract exhibited significant inhibition of HT115 colon cancer cell
577 invasion in the matrigel invasion assay. However, it did not affect epithelial integrity, as
578 assessed by the trans-epithelial resistance of Caco-2 cell monolayers (Coates *et al.*, 2007). In
579 the same year, other studies revealed that juices from raspberry, black currant, white currant,
580 gooseberry, blueberries, sea buckthorn, and cranberry strongly inhibited various cancer cell
581 lines, unlike strawberry or blackberry juice. Surprisingly, the anti-proliferative effects didn't
582 align with antioxidant capacity. Rather than apoptosis, cell-cycle arrest appeared to play a
583 role, along with the suppression of inflammatory pathways by certain berry juices (Boivin *et*
584 *al.*, 2007).

585 Overall, our previous studies on orange, beetroot, and apple juices, clearly showed that
586 normal FHs 74 Int cells exhibited greater resistance to fruit juices treated with CAPP
587 compared to Caco-2 cancer cells (Dzimitrowicz *et al.*, 2020; 2021; 2022).

588

589 3.5. Inactivation of *E. coli* and *S. cerevisiae* cells following FLC-dc-APGD RJ treatment

590 The included controls confirmed effective sterilization of the RJ prior to artificial inoculation
591 either with *E. coli* ATCC 25922 or *S. cerevisiae* FM26, as no colonies were observed after
592 plating the Microjet-sterilized samples on the TSA medium and incubation at 37°C for 24 hrs.
593 Here, the artificially inoculated freshly-squeezed RJ contained from 3×10^3 to 2.2×10^5 colony
594 forming units of *E. coli* ATCC 25922 per mL of the juice and due to the action of FLC-dc-
595 APGD all the bacterial cells have been successfully eradicated (Table 1). Therefore, it was
596 proven that the application of FLC-dc-APGD generated in the utilized reaction-discharge
597 system eliminated 100% of the studied model bacterial cells (Table 1). In terms of the model
598 fungal microorganism, *i.e.* *S. cerevisiae* FM26, lowering the microbial load from $3.3-5 \times 10^3$ to
599 $6.9 \times 10^2-1.34 \times 10^3$ has been achieved due to the FLC-dc-APGD exposure (Table 1). Thus, the
600 resultant percentage reductions in the amount of viable microbial cells varied from 73.2% to
601 79.5% (corresponding to 0.57-0.69 logarithmic reductions; Table 1), depending on the

602 repetition of the experiment. In summary, the herein described FLC-dc-APGD-generating
603 reaction discharge system turned out to be highly efficient in elimination of bacterial cells,
604 while boosting the inactivation rates towards fungi might be one of the future directions of the
605 follow-up research.

606 The herein described effectiveness of the CAPP-mediated inactivation of *E. coli* may
607 be juxtaposed, for instance, with the former study of Hosseini *et al.*, 2021. In that research,
608 the highest reduction of 6 logs in *E. coli* counts was noted in 5 mL of CAPP-exposed sour
609 cherry juice if the plasma subjection time, voltage and percentage of oxygen in argon
610 approximated the studied maxima of 9 min, 20 kV and 1%, respectively (Hosseini *et al.*,
611 2021). It may be stressed that the reaction-discharge system proposed in the current study
612 works in a flowing-through mode, which not only boosts the treated volume of the liquid, but
613 also limits the overall CAPP exposure period. Interestingly, we achieved similar to Hosseini
614 *et al.*, 2021 inactivation rates towards *E. coli*, without the need to use expensive noble gases.
615 Passing to another piece of research, it is worth to notice that Souza *et al.*, 2023 utilized the
616 same strain of *E. coli* (ATCC 25922) for artificial inoculation of orange juice before CAPP
617 treatment. There, a statistically significant reduction in bacterial count followed 1 min
618 exposure of 5 mL of the so-inoculated orange juice post subjection to DBD-type plasma,
619 though solely reduction from 5.86×10^4 to 4.88×10^3 CFU/mL has been achieved. In the
620 evoked work, also artificial inoculations of orange juice with fungal cells, *i.e.* *Candida*
621 *albicans* ATCC SC 5314, were conducted leading to minor, statistically insignificant CAPP-
622 mediated reductions from 1.74×10^4 to 1.53×10^4 CFU per mL (Souza *et al.*, 2023). This data
623 finds agreement with the herein reported observation on more challenging CAPP-driven
624 inactivation of fungal cells in contrast to the model bacteria.

625

626 6. Plasma-liquid interactions responsible for the properties of the CAPP-treated RJ

627 The short-lived RONS were identified *via* OES measurements. It can be seen in Figure 4 that
628 in the range of 315 to 380 nm several bands of N_2 from $C^3\Pi_u - B^3\Pi_g$ system with heads at
629 315.7 (1-0), 337.1 nm (0-0), 353.6 nm (1-2), 357.6 nm (0-1), 375.0 nm (1-3), and 380.4 nm
630 (0-2) were identified. Weak band belonging to N_2^+ molecules at 391.4 nm, were also noted.
631 Additionally, OH radicals from $A^2\Sigma^+ - X^2\Pi$ system with bandheads at 289.3 nm (1-0) and
632 309.2 nm (0-0) were likewise found in the OES spectrum, while the O lines were determined
633 at 777.2 nm, 777.4 nm and 844.7 nm. Finally, the H_β and H_α lines with heads at 486.1 nm and
634 656.2 nm have been recognized. It is also worth to mention that the recorded OES spectrum
635 well correlates with the ICP-OES measurements for the quantitative determination of the

636 selected elements. In the presented OES spectrum, a weak atomic line of Zn I was identified
637 at 214.1 nm. Additionally, a strong line of Mg I at 285.4 nm was observed in the OES
638 spectrum along with Cu I at 324.7 nm, Ca I at 422.4 nm, Na I at 589.0 and 589.5 nm, as well
639 as K I at 776.5 and 769.9 nm.

640 Referring to the identified short-lived RONS, resulting most likely from interactions
641 between FLC-dc-APGD and RJ, OH^\bullet along with $^1\text{O}_2$, $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$, HO_2^\bullet , O_3 , as well as N_2^\bullet and N^\bullet
642 might have been generated in the first-order reactions. To provide deeper insight into the
643 contributions of certain RONS present in the CAPP-treated RJ of before-reported anticancer
644 activity (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2019), the concentration of H_2O_2 was determined. The appearance
645 of H_2O_2 in the CAPP-treated samples is common and directly linked with the second-order
646 recombination reaction of OH^\bullet (Wandell *et al.*, 2019). It was determined that in the FLC-dc-
647 APGD-treated RJ the contents of H_2O_2 reached $2.52 \pm 0.26 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, while in the untreated
648 samples these molecules were not detected at all. It should be noted that the determined H_2O_2
649 concentration may be considered rather high compared with other CAPP sources and the
650 treated matrixes. For instance, 120-s application of CAPP plasmajet generated under argon
651 atmosphere on 2 mL of apple juice lead to formation of 3 - 10 mg L^{-1} of H_2O_2 (Surowsky *et al.*,
652 2014). In another study, the application of CAPP under atmospheric air for treatment of
653 3.00 mL of apple juice for 5 s resulted in production of 2 mg L^{-1} of H_2O_2 (Liao *et al.*, 2018).
654 In juxtaposition to the studies referred above, the H_2O_2 concentration herein obtained by using
655 the FLC-dc-APGD system for treatment of RJ can be regarded as considerable and might be
656 responsible for the observed biological effect. The determined concentration of NO_2^- was 5.00
657 $\pm 0.38 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ for the FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ investigated in the current study, while in the
658 case of the corresponding untreated RJ, this matrix completely lacked the analysed ions. As a
659 result of second-order reactions that might consume NO and H_2O_2 or O_3 , the presence of NO_2^-
660 may indirectly point to the abundance of NO_x in the plasma-liquid interactions, as well as
661 explain the revealed anticancer properties of the CAPP-treated RJ (Mintz *et al.*, 2021).

662 The herein described physiochemical changes in RJ following FLC-dc-APGD
663 treatment along with the triggered inhibition of Caco-2 cells may be most likely linked with
664 the generated H_2O_2 and NO_2^- reactive representatives. As RJ remains a complex matrix, the
665 plasma-liquid interactions occur abundantly, leading to effective scavenging of a broad
666 spectrum, CAPP-delivered radicals or generation of products with these reactive species,
667 which could pose certain cytotoxicity towards the examined cancer cell lines.

668

669 **4. Conclusions**

670 This is the first study in which the effects of cold atmospheric pressure plasma (CAPP)
671 treatment, in this case *via* direct current atmospheric pressure glow discharge generated in
672 contact with a flowing liquid cathode (FLC-dc-AGPD), were assessed in relation to
673 physicochemical, nutritional, microbiological, and cytotoxic properties of the freshly
674 squeezed raspberry juice. Here, we reported retention of physicochemical and nutritional
675 properties of the so-treated RJ, while at the same time bacterial *E. coli* cells were completely
676 eradicated during the applied CAPP exposure. The current FLC-dc-APGD treatment was
677 proven less efficient against fungal *S. cerevisiae* cells, anyway leading to elimination of 73.2-
678 79.5% of the subjected cells. Interestingly, RJ post FLC-dc-AGPD action exhibited cytotoxic
679 properties towards human colon adenocarcinoma (Caco-2) cell line, contrarily to FHs 74 Int
680 normal human intestinal epithelial cell line. After optimization in a direction to improve
681 elimination of fungal cells and appropriate follow-up studies on biosafety of the CAPP-
682 mediated preservation, we believe that the herein proposed approach might be a tempting
683 alternative for the food-processing sector.

684

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691

692 **Conflicts of Interest**

693 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

694

695 **Author Contributions**

696 A.D., P.J., A.M.P., W.S., and P.P. conceptualized this work. A.D., P.J., and D.T. adapted the FLC-dc-
697 APGD-based continuous flow system for RJ treatment under stable operating conditions. A.D., W.S.,
698 W.B.W., and P.P. prepared the portion of freshly squeezed RJ for FLC-dc-APGD treatment. M.C.
699 performed studies related to HPLC-DAD and GC-MS and described the collected chromatograms.
700 P.C. and P.J. were responsible for the determination of selected physicochemical properties of FLC-
701 dc-APGD-treated and untreated RJ and analyzed the obtained outcomes. P.P. carried out the elemental
702 analyses and described the obtained results. P.J. and D.T. determined plasma-liquid interactions in the
703 gaseous or liquid phase of the CAPP studied and described the results. W.S., A.M.P., and W.B.W
704 conducted microbiological studies. A.M.P described and interpreted the performed microbiological

705 assays. A.B.P. and A.K. determined the cytotoxic properties of the FLC-dc-APGD-treated and
706 untreated RJ and analyzed the results. P.P., A.D., M.C., P.J., and A.M.P. were involved in the
707 preparation of the first draft of this article. All authors participated in discussions. A.D. collected
708 comments from all co-authors and prepared the final version of the manuscript. All Authors corrected
709 the manuscript. A.D. was responsible for project admission and raw data storage. All Authors agreed
710 to final version of the manuscript.

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901

902 **Figure 1.** Overlapped GC-MS chromatograms (as total ion currents) of the untreated and

903 FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ

904

905

906 **Figure 2.** Overlapped HPLC-DAD chromatograms of the untreated and the FLC-dc-APGD-
907 treated RJ.

A) 24H

72H

B)

909 **Figure 3.** The cell proliferation activity exposed to raspberry juice (RJ) untreated (UNTR RJ)
910 and FLC-dc-APGD treated (FLC-APGD RJ). **a)** The morphology of normal human intestinal
911 epithelial cell line (FHs 74 Int) and human colonic adenocarcinoma cell line (Caco-2)
912 incubated with untreated raspberry juice (UNTR RJ) and FLC-dcAPGD-treated raspberry
913 juice (FLC-APGD RJ) at different concentrations ($\times 1000$; $\times 100$; $\times 25$; $\times 10$) were investigated.
914 The incubation was performed for 24 h and 72 h. The pictures were taken using a Zeiss
915 Primovert Inverted Microscope instrument, bar represents 100 μm ; **b)** The proliferation was
916 investigated as the measurement of the absorbance at 570 nm. The data shown are means \pm
917 standard deviations of the mean values for three analyses done in duplicate. The statistical
918 comparison was performed by using the one-way ANOVA test with Dunnett's post *hoc test*
919 and compared to the CONTROL medium group (the cells treated with the medium alone); *p
920 < 0.05 , **p < 0.01 , ***p < 0.001 .

OES spectra of FLC-APGD and RJ interaction zone

921

922 **Figure 4.** The OES spectrum acquired from discharge zone between FLC-dc-APGD and the
923 flowing RJ in the range from 200 to 400 nm (above) and 400-900 nm (below).

924 **Table 1.** Efficacy of microbial eradication from the artificially-inoculated freshly-squeezed sterile RJ

Repetition	Initial microbial count, CFU mL ⁻¹	Microbial count post plasma treatment, CFU mL ⁻¹	Percentage reduction, %	Logarithmic reduction
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 25922				
I	2×10^5	0	100	Complete
II	3×10^3	0	100	Complete
III	2.2×10^5	0	100	Complete
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> FM26				
I	3.3×10^3	6.9×10^2	79.1	0.68
II	5×10^3	1.34×10^3	73.2	0.57
III	4.3×10^3	8.8×10^2	79.5	0.69

925 CFU – colony forming units

926

927 **Table 2.** Volatile compounds identified by SPME-GC-MS in the untreated and FLC-dc-
928 APGD-treated RJ (according to the library search).

929

Compound name	Retention time, min	Library match, %
cis-3-hexenal	8.9	93
hexyl-hydroxyperoxide	9.0	93
5-methyl-2-hexanone	9.3	95
2-heptanol	9.4	97
β -linalol	12.0	91
α -terpinelol	13.3	91
guaniol (trans-geraniol, lemonol, nerol)	13.8	91
α -ionol	15.3	92
α -ionone	16.0	93
β -ionone	16.7	95

930

931 **Table 3.** Color indexes, *i.e.*, lightness L , red to green increments a and blue to yellow
 932 increments b measured in the untreated and the FLC-dc-APGD-treated RJ (n=3).

	L	a	b
Untreated	54.5 ($\pm 0.1\%$)	3.85 ($\pm 0.7\%$)	2.49 ($\pm 0.6\%$)
FLC-dc-APGD- treated	54.3 ($\pm 0.1\%$)	3.34 ($\pm 1.1\%$)	2.28 ($\pm 1.0\%$)
Relative difference	-0.1%	-13.3%	-8.4%

933 Average values along with standard deviations

934

935 **Table 4.** Concentrations (in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) of the selected elements in the untreated and the FLC-dc-
 936 APGD-treated RJ (n=3).

	Untreated ^a	FLC-dc-APGD-treated ^a	Relative difference, %
Al	0.283 ± 0.034	0.287 ± 0.007	+1.4
Ba	0.121 ± 0.003	0.120 ± 0.002	-0.9
Ca	114 ± 1	130 ± 2	+13.9
Cu	0.323 ± 0.027	0.313 ± 0.018	-3.1
Fe	1.38 ± 0.17	1.36 ± 0.19	-1.6
K	1640 ± 20	1680 ± 10	+2.5
Mg	144 ± 1	145 ± 1	+0.5
Mn	1.06 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.01	-0.3
Na	4.99 ± 0.04	5.73 ± 0.06	+14.7
Sr	0.303 ± 0.008	0.300 ± 0.005	-0.9
Zn	1.80 ± 0.07	2.07 ± 0.08	14.6%

937 ^a Average values along with standard deviations

938